

Polychelates of Zinc(II), Titanium(III), Oxovanadium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) Ions with Polymeric Schiff Bases of Thiazole Derivatives

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The facile regenerability, higher stability and operational flexibility¹ of the coordination polymers has created considerable research interest in recent years². Although scanty details are available on polychelates of polystyrene supported ligands³ but practically nothing has been done on the polymers of Schiff bases of thiazoles. This communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of some polymeric ligands derived from thiazole derivatives and their polychelates with Zn^{II}, Ti^{III}, VO^{IV} and UO₂^{VI} ions.

Results and Discussion

The polychelates were found insoluble in most of the solvents. Repeated elution of even DMF could not produce any measurable value of molar conductance indicating non-electrolytic nature of the polychelates. The average molecular weights determined by vapour pressure osmometry, and the chemical analysis data (Table 1) agree with 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The lower values of molecular weights reflecting lower degree of polymerisation, indicates the presence of linear polymeric ligands. This is supported by the fact that an *ortho*-position occupied Schiff base can not produce a cross-linked polymer with 1,2-dichloroethane.

In the ir spectra, the broad weak band at 2 900 cm⁻¹ due to hydrogen bonded phenolic OH stretch of the ligands, disappeared in the spectra of the polychelates, indicating deprotonation of OH and its involvement in coordination. The shift of ν (phenolic CO) from 1 300 to 1 320 cm⁻¹, supports this⁴. Two ligand bands at 1 580 and 1 620 cm⁻¹ due to central C=N and ring C=N stretch respectively⁵, shifted to 1 610 and

1 630 cm⁻¹ on chelation confirming the coordination through azomethine group⁵. Appearance of new bands at 1 570, 800 and 600 cm⁻¹ in the polychelates of Ti^{III} and VO^{IV} confirmed the presence of coordinated water⁴. The bands at 960 and 930 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of vanadyl and uranyl polychelates were attributed to ν (V=O) and ν_{as} (O=U=O) (ν_3) modes⁶. The absence of 850 cm⁻¹ band confirms the linearity of UO₂^{II} ion in the uranyl polychelates⁷.

The Zn^{II} and UO₂^{VI} polychelates are diamagnetic as expected. Reflectance spectra of the uranyl polychelates exhibit bands at 19 000, 23 000 and 39 000 cm⁻¹ consistent with the vibronic structure of the triatomic entity of UO₂^{II} group⁸. The Ti^{III} polychelates having magnetic moments 1.68 and 1.75 B.M., gave a band at 20 000 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at 18 700 cm⁻¹, which is due to the transition ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ showing octahedral geometry of the chelates. The polychelates of VO^{IV} had magnetic moments 1.65, 1.70 B.M. and exhibited reflectance bands at 13 000, 18 000, 23 000, 32 000 and 38 000 cm⁻¹ due to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ($b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($b_2 \rightarrow a^*$) and charge transfer transitions, the characteristic feature of octahedral complexes⁹.

A weight-loss equivalent to one and two water molecules at 186 and 178° in TG and the corresponding endothermic peaks in DTA in case of the VO^{IV} and Ti^{III} polychelates indicated the presence of one and two coordinated water molecules in these cases¹⁰. Other polychelates are stable upto ~ 250°. The thermal stability of polymeric ligands was found to be more than the polychelates because of the presence of

hydrogen bonds in the ligands. Thermal stability was in the order : ligand > UO_2^{VI} > Zn^{II} > VO^{IV} > Ti^{III} polychelates, in confirmity with the reported results¹¹.

On the basis of the above studies the following structures were proposed to the polychelates :

X = zero for Zn^{II} and UO_2^{VI} ; H_2O for Ti^{III} and VO^{IV}
 Y = zero for Zn^{II} , VO^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} ; H_2O for Ti^{III}

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (Sarabhai) was distilled before use. 1,2-Dichloroethane (Sigma) and other chemicals (A. R., B.D.H.) were used as such. The solvents (Glaxo or E. Merck) were distilled twice before use.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole was prepared by the reported method¹². 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole was synthesised by diazotisation of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole. Sodium nitrite (1.4 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in water (20 ml) was gradually added to a well-cooled solution of aniline (1.85 g, 0.02 mol) in 2N HCl (25 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered to a cold suspension of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (3.5 g, 0.02 mol) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After constant stirring for 1 h, the mixture was left for 2 h. The separated 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole was washed several times with water and crystallised from DMF-ethanol (1 : 1, v/v), m.p. 193°.

Schiff bases : These were synthesised by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-benzaldehyde with the respective thiazole derivatives. For the synthesis of 2-

hydroxy-1-benzylidene-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole, 2-hydroxy-1-benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was added to solution of 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole (0.01 mol) in benzene (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for some time. The separated water was removed through a Dean-Stark trap. The resulting solid was crystallised from absolute alcohol as shining orange needles, m.p. 189°; ν_{max} 2 900 (H-bonded OH), 1 620 and 1 580 cm^{-1} (salicylalimine). Similarly, 2-hydroxy-1-benzylidene-2-aminobenzo-thiazole was synthesised, m.p. 201°.

Polymeric Schiff base ligands : To a well-cooled (4–6°) and stirred mixture of alcoholic solution of the Schiff base (0.05 mol; 20 ml) and 1,2-dichloroethane (0.1 mol; 9 ml), powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (25 g) was added slowly (15 min). The reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and then refluxed on a steam-bath for 5–6 h. On cooling, the mixture was treated with ice-cold aqueous 10% HCl (20 ml) and the resulting brown coloured solid was washed with alcohol and then steam-distilled to remove excess of the reactants. The solid left was dissolved in minimum quantity of aqueous NaOH and then reprecipitated by the addition of ice-cold aqueous 10% HCl. The solid was washed with water and dried at room temperature. It was found soluble in dioxane, DMF and DMSO.

Polychelates : To the polymeric ligand (0.01 mol) dissolved in DMF (25 ml), a suspensions of the metal ions (titanium chloride, vanadyl sulphate and nitrates of Zn^{II} and UO_2^{VI}) in DMF-alcohol (0.005 mol in 30 ml; 1 : 1, v/v) were added dropwise with constant stirring. A saturated solution of ammonium acetate (20 g) was then added with rapid stirring. On refluxing the mixture on a water-bath at 70° for 1 h, the solid polychelates were separated. These were washed with DMF-alcohol-water mixture (1 : 1 : 1, v/v) and dried at 60°.

The physical methods followed were the same as reported earlier¹³.

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TABLE I - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE POLYMERIC LIGANDS AND POLYCHELATES

Compd./ (Colour)	Melting range °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
		Metal	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen	
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S}(\text{L}_1)$ (Brown)	280-90	—	70.70 (70.59)	5.00 4.90	9.00 9.15)	—
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2\text{S}(\text{L}_2)$ (Brown)	274-80	—	68.25 (68.57)	4.00 4.29	10.18 10.00)	—
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_1)_2]_n$ (Cream)	246-60	9.87 (9.71)	64.00 64.15	4.00 4.16	8.00 8.32)	Diamag
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_2)_2]_2$ (Cream)	240-48	10.20 (10.49)	61.75 61.80	3.75 3.53	9.00 8.98)	Diamag.
$[\text{Li}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ (Purple)	174-80	(7.00 (7.30)	66.00 65.86	4.00 4.27	8.30 8.54)	1.68
$[\text{Ti}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ (Purple)	178-84	8.00 (7.90)	63.52 63.38	3.75 3.63	9.00 9.24)	1.75
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_n$ (Chocolate)	180-88	7.50 (7.35)	62.50 62.34	4.30 4.04	8.20 8.08)	1.65
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_n$ (Brown)	180-85	8.00 (7.92)	59.50 59.72	4.50 3.42	8.52 8.71)	1.70
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_1)_2]_n$ (Orange)	258-66	25.00 (26.29)	52.10 52.30	3.50 3.39	6.52 6.78)	Diamag
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_2)_2]_n$ (Orange)	252-62	28.00 (28.10)	49.75 49.48	3.00 2.83	7.00 7.22)	Diamag.

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